

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of human capital and proactive personality on career success with career motivation as mediation and career management support as moderation in private lecturers

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Abstract

This quantitative study investigates the complex relationship between proactive personality, human resources and career success, which is mediated by career motivation and added moderating variables by career management support to the relationship between career motivation and career success among lecturers in Indonesia. This research is an explanatory quantitative research that examines and analyses the influence of variables in the research hypothesis using the basis of career construction theory (CCT). The sample is 400 private lecturers LLDIKTI 1 – LLDIKTI 16, Indonesia. The survey method is used to collect sample data and uses the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis technique with PLS software. This research confirms the suitability of the test instrument and model, accepting the eight hypotheses, with the influence of human capital being more dominant than proactive personality and career motivation. Career support management acts as a moderator variable which shows that management support increases individual career success. The implication is that universities must pay attention to human resources and proactive personalities to increase career success supported by career management. The success of a lecturer's career supports the success of the university.

Keywords: Career; Human Capital; Management Support; Motivation; Proactive Personality.

1. Introduction

Every company must hold onto employees who attain success in their professions, as those who excel in their careers can provide valuable performance that bolsters the organization [1]. Ongoing dedication to enhancing human capital markedly affects the continual progression of individual careers [2], [3]. As outlined in research carried out by [4], a substantial reservoir of human capital also plays a pivotal role in reaching elevated standards of job proficiency, wisdom, and aptitude, subsequently paving the way for elevation to more advanced career stages. Because accomplishments in a career path are established over time, individual career management frequently focuses on career success [5]. Subjective professional success and objective career success are two of the main variables that help explain career achievement [6]. Career success can be seen as a personal assessment of one's professional achievements, according to [7], and is influenced by both one's experience and their own subjective judgment of their professional attainments, as noted by [8]. A person's job success, on the other hand, can be measured objectively and includes things like salary, position, hierarchical rank, number of promotions, level of career advancement, and pay raises [9] [10], [11].

The research objects for lecturers have special unique characteristics, which make perspectives among researchers. Research on lecturer career success is viewed from a greater objectivity perspective, for example the ability to have high human capital and proactive personality [12]. Human Capital is a well-established investment known to significantly impact lecturers for the purpose of achieving sustainable progress in their careers [2], [3]. Lecturers who

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have high investment in human capital will also get higher income opportunities [4]. Because high human capital will provide greater job proficiency, knowledge, and skills so as to realize higher career level promotion opportunities [13]. In addition, what helps the career success of lecturers is the proactive personality of [14] and [15]. It was explained that proactive personality is the tendency of lecturers to take an active role in promoting themselves or others towards the surrounding environment. For example, lecturers spontaneously solve problems, propose innovative ideas, seek information about hierarchical status, ask for feedback, engage in dedication [16], [17], [18].

Various viewpoints regarding the connection between measurable and personal professional achievements have been highlighted in prior studies on individual career growth. Certain studies argue that one's subjective perception of professional success affects their objective career accomplishments [19]. Some research asserts that achieving objective career success positively impacts an individual's subjective perception of their career accomplishments [20]. However, other study has found that subjective and objective professional success are linked and form a single concept known as total career success. Career satisfaction is commonly used as an impartial indicator of professional success. However, there is only a negligible degree of association between subjective and objective career success [6]. This result lends credence to the idea that these two conceptions can be distinguished or are largely independent. As a result, "overall career success" refers to the confirmation of both subjective and objective career success.

Individual career success is an intriguing topic that promotes individual professional development, according to various prior research evaluations. However, there is little study on how individuals succeed in their careers in non-profits. Individual career management in non-profit organizations is described by [21] as the actions taken by an individual to develop their career. The term "career protean" refers to this idea, which was first proposed by [22] and which later gained wider recognition in 1996.

The career management assistance variable is included in this study's focus on lecturer careers as a moderating variable in educational research. Success in a lecturer's career in higher education is valued as the key component of national education, which is anticipated to evolve into a hub for higher education and scientific advancement. The primary goal of the institution is to advance and apply knowledge through Tri Dharma, with professors serving as the principal resource. This study emphasizes on the responsibilities of lecturers in upholding the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, which includes learning and teaching, research, and civic engagement. The careers of lecturers in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, including those of civil servants and independent scholars, are regulated in the functional position of lecturer.

There is a shortage of professors at universities in Indonesia, namely only 5,576 people, or around 2.3% of the total 236,255 lecturers who hold positions as State Civil Apparatus (ASN). In addition, as many as 83,881 lecturers (around 35.5%) do not have functional positions (Kemenristekdikti, 2021). In fact, Professors are individuals who have the highest responsibility as holders of knowledge together with young colleagues and postgraduate students. The main duties of Professors include conducting research, publications and seeking research funding, all of which aim to strengthen the good name and authority of higher education institutions.

Five constructs are used in this study: proactivity, individual human capital (which includes qualities like leadership and motivation, qualifications, satisfaction, and creativity), career motivation (which includes qualities like career insight, career resilience, and career identity), and career success (which combines subjective and objective measures). Support for career management (Subjective: Career Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction, and Objective: Job Promotion, Compensation, and Job Stagnation). This study differs from earlier research in that it focuses on lecturers in tertiary institutions, or educational organizations, rather than profit-oriented organizations like big businesses, and it validates the combination of subjective and objective factors in career success in addition to including career management support variables as a moderating factor.

This research seeks to accomplish several objectives. Firstly, it aims to assess how proactive personality and human capital influence one's career success. Secondly, it aims to explore the indirect influence of proactive personality and human capital on career success through career motivation. Furthermore, it aims to comprehend how proactive personality and human capital influence one's drive for a successful career. Finally, the objective is to evaluate how career success is affected by career motivation and to investigate how mentorship in career management can alter the connection between career motivation and career success.

Proactive Personality, as defined by [23], refers to individuals who actively seek and create opportunities to enhance their performance in the workplace. It is characterized by a stable trait known as proactive disposition, where individuals challenge the status quo rather than conforming to existing circumstances [24]. Those with a proactive personality tend to excel because they possess the skills and knowledge to identify and capitalize on opportunities,

leading to greater career achievements. They actively seek career-related information, support, and self-development opportunities [25]. This proactive approach is crucial in navigating uncertain workplace environments, as proactive individuals actively seek new resources and opportunities to advance their careers. Consequently, they consistently outperform their peers by effectively managing the generation and execution of opportunities. H1: Proactive personality has a significant influence on career success.

Investing in one's human capital, as substantiated by research from [2], [3], [26], holds a profound influence on long-term career progression. This investment enhances employability, knowledge, and transferable skills, enabling individuals to negotiate better salaries, as emphasized by [27], [4]. Rich human capital opens doors to career advancement across diverse industries, aligning with [13] insights.

Moreover, a robust human capital base empowers individuals to meet performance expectations across various roles, a concept highlighted by [28], [29]. Thus, those with elevated human capital are more likely to achieve career success. This framework integrates demographic factors, human capital investment, personal traits, social learning, and motivation theories, underscoring individual attributes' role in achieving career prosperity. In competitive career landscapes, where some outperform others, human capital consistently emerges as the key factor, as posited by [30]. Investing in human capital equips individuals with professional skills, enhances workplace productivity, and positively impacts compensation structures, aligning with [31]'s findings. H2: Human capital has a significant influence on career success.

The concept of Proactive Personality, as discussed by [32], pertains to individuals who actively seek opportunities and take initiative, displaying a strong drive to initiate and successfully implement career changes. Proactive individuals are characterized by their flexibility and sense of ownership over long-term career goals beyond their immediate job responsibilities, as noted by [33]. This multifaceted construct, influenced by personal and organizational factors [34], encompasses determination, willpower, and motivation, all crucial qualities in the self-development model proposed by [21]. In a comprehensive study, [35] discovered favorable connections among proactive personality, innovation, political knowledge, and career motivation. These factors, in turn, exhibited positive correlations with advancing in one's career and experiencing job satisfaction. [36] defined a proactive personality as one that takes initiative to enhance environmental quality. [37] research demonstrated that proactive individuals exhibit high motivation levels, confirming a robust and favorable correlation between proactive actions and career motivation. Based on these findings, it can be deduced that individuals exhibiting proactive traits show heightened motivation to advance in their prospective careers. H3: Proactive personality has a significant influence on career motivation.

In the study of career competition motivations, as highlighted by [30], individuals often seek to understand the driving forces behind career advancement within organizational contexts. Swifter promotions are frequently attributed to individuals possessing substantial human capital, a concept elaborated upon by [31]. Human capital, in a comprehensive sense, encompasses factors like work hours invested, tenure with an organization, professional experience, willingness to engage in international work, educational achievements, career planning, knowledge, and political acumen all of which are influenced by an individual's Career Motivation. Career motivation is a complex internal construct, shaped by various situational factors, and is manifested through individual decisions and behaviors. The choice of career [38], criteria for measuring success [39], and the development of human capital [40] have been extensively explored in relation to career motivation. Prior research has delved into relevant literature on career success, resulting in the formulation of theoretical frameworks and hypotheses that can be empirically examined to explore the interconnections between human capital, alignment with the work environment, organizational support, and career motivation. H4: Human capital has a significant influence on career motivation.

A substantial level of human capital serves as a concise indicator to organizations that job candidates are well-suited for employment due to their amassed job-relevant knowledge. Individuals with a significant human capital profile tend to readily access new career opportunities and diverse experiences, as demonstrated by [41]. Investing in human resources has been established as a potent driver of sustained career progression, as supported by research from [2], [42]. Similarly, human capital enhancement can bolster an individual's capacity to meet the performance expectations of various roles, a concept examined by [38]. Therefore, most likely people with high levels of human capital tend to be supported by high career motivation in achieving the desired career success [43]. Thus, it is clear that Career Motivation plays a crucial role as a robust intermediary factor in the connection between Human Capital and career achievement. H5: Human capital influences career success mediated by career motivation.

Numerous studies have consistently highlighted the positive association between a proactive personality and various aspects of career success and satisfaction. Research by [44], [45] has shown that individuals possessing proactive personalities often enjoy higher levels of career satisfaction and contentment in their jobs. Moreover, empirical

evidence, as emphasized by [46], establishes a clear link between proactive personality and objective career success. The underlying reason for this positive correlation is rooted in the concept that proactive individuals consistently engage in proactive behaviors, as articulated by [45]. These individuals exhibit a consistent inclination to take initiative across diverse activities and circumstances, actively shaping their environments. From the perspective of career success, proactive behavior is closely aligned with the journey to success, particularly when it is supported by Career Motivation, as proposed by [47]. Personality traits, including proactivity, not only directly impact career success but also indirectly influence it through their effects on motivation. H6: Proactive personality influences career success mediated by career motivation.

The organization is a supporting bridge in management related to career development programs that are provided as a process of support in achieving career success for its members [48], [49]. Therefore, individuals with heightened career motivation are likely to realize the career success they aim for [43]. That way, there is no doubt that career motivation is a strong connecting variable in the career success relationship [48]. Career motivation is conceptualized as an individual's internal multidimensional construct that is influenced by situations, and is reflected in individual decisions and behavior. H7: Career motivation has a significant influence on career success.

The organization is a supporting bridge in management related to career development programs that are provided as a process of support in achieving career success for its members [48], [49]. With career management support, it is hoped that organizations can plan well to support each individual for career success. Career management support typically encompasses a range of deliberate organizational policies and practices designed to enhance the individual's effectiveness in their career pursuits. While the specifics of these programs can differ, they generally include activities like understanding employees' career aspirations, offering suitable career paths, determining deserving candidates for these opportunities, and assessing the outcomes of career management initiatives [50]. On the other hand, individual career management represents personal initiatives taken by individuals to pursue their personal career goals, which may or may not be in sync with their organization's objectives [51], [34]. The concept of shared responsibility, as explored in this research, presupposes that achieving career effectiveness entails not only individual efforts but also the provision of suitable career management programs by the employer. As per the psychological success model, employees proactively employ career management programs to align with their personal career objectives, involving a sequence of well-considered and systematic individual choices become plans to contribute to career success [52], [30], [21]. H8: Career motivation influences career success moderated by career management support.

Source: compiled by the author

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

This study employed a quantitative methodology. Indicators are employed as measures for each of the five variables in this research that cannot be measured directly, utilizing a study of structural equation modelling (SEM).

Based on statistical information from the PDDIKTI (Higher Education Database), the study's analytical unit consisted of lecturers with the status of teaching staff and expert assistants who are members of LLDIKTI 1 through LLDIKTI 16 throughout Indonesia. The following is a list of the sample criteria:

- Private permanent lecturer employed by PDDIKTI (based on secondary data from the 2020 Higher Education Statistics).

- Private permanent professors with NIDN who do not yet hold the minimum rank and functional position of assistant expert but have had it for at least a year.
- Private, tenure-track lecturers who only conduct research and are not practitioners.
- Private permanent lecturers who have not been promoted, at least an expert assistant with a minimum of 1 year.
- The number of lecturers who did not yet have functional positions was 165,840 thousand lecturers, and expert assistants were 109,398 thousand lecturers, bringing the total to 275,238 thousand lecturers. This information was derived based on secondary data statistics for higher education for 2020.
- Applying the Slovin formula with a 5% margin of error, a sample size of 400 lecturers was calculated.

3. Result and Discussions

3.1. Convergent Validity Test

Several criteria are used to test the convergent validity of each indicator on the variables of proactive personality, human resources, career motivation, career management support and career success. First, evaluate convergent validity based on AVE (Average Variance Extracted) and outer loading. Valid indicators have outer loading and AVE less than 0.50 [53]. T-statistic values can also be used to assess the validity of indicators; an indicator is considered valid if the T-statistic value exceeds 1.96 or the p-value is less than 5% [53]. These standards will be used to determine whether the convergent validity of each indicator for the variable's proactive personality, human resources, career motivation, career management support, and career success.

Source: Output SEM Smart PLS

Figure 2 Outer loading

All indicators on the variables proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, career management support, and career success have acquired outer loading values more than 0.50, according to the results of the final phases of convergent validity testing. These findings support the assertion that all indicators are valid for measuring the constructs of human capital, career motivation, and career success because they all meet the criteria for convergent validity.

3.2. Discriminant Validity Test

Additionally, utilizing the cross-loading approach, the Fornell-Larcker criterion, and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), outer model analysis was done to assess discriminant validity. We will concentrate on the HTMT results in this instance because they are thought to be a new criterion that is more effective at evaluating discriminant validity. [54] Given that a value of HTMT greater than 0.90 is thought to indicate weak discriminant validity, demonstrating discriminant validity necessitates a value of HTMT less than 0.90. It is possible to conclude from the results of this analysis that all indicators of proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, career management support and career success have satisfactorily complied with the requirements for discriminant validity.

Table 1 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Value

Construct	X1	X2	Z1	Z2	Y
Proactive Personality (X1)					
Human Capital (X2)	0.270				
Career Motivation (Z1)	0.472	0.526			
Career Management Support (Z2)	0.352	0.406	0.498		
Career Success (Y)	0.464	0.520	0.535	0.662	

Source: processed field data

The table above shows that the HTMT value for all combinations of constructs produces a value smaller than the maximum limit of 0.90 [53], so it can be concluded that the variables are proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, career management support, and career success. has fulfilled discriminant validity.

3.3. Analysis of Coefficients of Determination (R^2)

The assessment of the internal model's effectiveness is gauged through the R^2 value, also known as the coefficient of determination. Level R^2 has a value range of 0-1. [53] explained that it is in the substantial category, namely 0.75, moderate at 0.50 and weak at 0.25. Following are the results of calculating R^2 for each endogenous construct.

Table 2 Coefficient of Determination

Endogenous Construct	R-Square	Category
Career Motivation (Z1)	0.330	Weak
Career Success (Y)	0.513	Moderate

Source: processed field data

Using SEM-PLS data analysis, the R^2 value for the career motivation variable is 0.330, indicating that proactive personality and human capital collectively account for 33.0% of the influence on career motivation. This falls within the weak category, implying the presence of numerous other variables that also impact lecturers' career motivation. Furthermore, the R^2 value for the career success variable is 0.513, signifying that proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, and career management support jointly contribute to 51.3% of the influence on career success, categorizing it as moderate.

3.4. Direct Effect Significance Analysis

To assess the significance of the pathways of influence between variables based on the research hypothesis, the Smart PLS software is utilized. This includes reviewing the path coefficient table generated from bootstrapping results. In a two-sided test, the research hypothesis is considered valid when the t-count (T-statistic) is 1.96 or higher, or if the p-value is less than the specified error threshold (α) of 5%. Below are the original sample estimate values for path coefficients, corresponding t-count (T-statistic) values, and the associated p-values within the resulting model obtained from the PLS Bootstrapping main model.

Table 3 Direct Effect Significance Test Results

Direct Influence	Coeff	T-Stat	P-Value	Remark
Proactive Personality (X1) → Career Success (Y)	0.193	5.039	0.000	H1 accepted
Human Capital (X2) → Career Success (Y)	0.219	5.788	0.000	H2 accepted
Proactive Personality (X1) → Career Motivation (Z1)	0.342	9.533	0.000	H3 accepted
Human Capital (X2) → Career Motivation (Z1)	0.385	9.098	0.000	H4 accepted
Career Motivation (Z1) → Career Success (Y)	0.123	2.805	0.000	H7 accepted

Source: processed field data

The outcomes of hypothesis testing, as derived from the PLS bootstrapping results presented in the table above, can be elucidated as follows:

Proactive personality significantly and positively influences career success, with a coefficient of 0.193 indicating a strong positive relationship. The t-count of 5.039 surpasses the threshold of 1.96, and the p-value of 0.000 is below 5%. Thus, it is confirmed that proactive personality has a positive and statistically significant impact on career success. This suggests that lecturers with a higher level of proactive personality, demonstrated by their active pursuit of opportunities, initiative-taking, and persistent goal pursuit, are more likely to achieve favorable career success. These results affirm the acceptance of the first hypothesis, which posits that proactive personality influences career success in lecturers (H1 is accepted).

Human capital demonstrates a significant and favorable impact on career success, with a coefficient of 0.219 suggesting a positive association. The t-count of 5.788 exceeds the threshold of 1.96, and the p-value is 0.000, lower than 5%. Thus, it is confirmed that human capital has a constructive and statistically significant effect on career success. This implies that the greater the extent of valuable human capital possessed by a university, which proves beneficial in addressing various challenges to achieve organizational objectives, the more favorable the career success of lecturers affiliated with that university is likely to be. These findings support the acceptance of the second hypothesis, which posits that human capital influences career success among lecturers (H2 is accepted).

A proactive personality significantly and positively influences career motivation, with a coefficient value of 0.342 indicating a strong positive connection. The t-count of 9.533 surpasses the threshold of 1.96, and the p-value is 0.000, falling below 5%. Therefore, it is affirmed that proactive personality has a favorable and statistically significant impact on career motivation. This suggests that the higher a lecturer's proactive personality is, characterized by their inclination to actively seek opportunities, display initiative, take decisive action, and demonstrate persistence in achieving goals, the higher their level of career motivation is likely to be. Based on these findings, the third hypothesis, which posits that proactive personality influences career motivation among lecturers, is validated (H3 is accepted).

Human capital significantly and positively impacts career motivation, with a coefficient of 0.385 indicating a strong positive correlation. The t-count of 9.098 exceeds the threshold of 1.96, and the p-value is 0.000, falling below 5%. Thus, it is confirmed that human capital has a substantial and statistically significant effect on career motivation. Consequently, it is confirmed that human capital also has a constructive and statistically significant impact on career motivation. This implies that the greater the extent of valuable human capital possessed by a university, which proves beneficial in addressing various challenges to achieve organizational goals, the higher the career motivation of lecturers affiliated with that university is likely to be. These findings support the acceptance of the fourth hypothesis, which posits that human capital influences career motivation among lecturers (H4 is accepted).

Career motivation exerts a noticeable and positive influence on career success. The coefficient value representing the impact of career motivation on career success is 0.123, indicating a positive correlation. The associated t-count stands at 3.887, surpassing the threshold of 1.96, and the p-value is 0.005, which is less than 5%. As a result, it is established that career motivation also has a beneficial and statistically significant impact on career success. This implies that the higher a lecturer's level of career motivation, the more elevated their career success is likely to be. These findings affirm the acceptance of the seventh hypothesis, which suggests that career motivation influences career success among lecturers (H7 is accepted).

3.5. Indirect Effect Significance Analysis

The assessment of the indirect impact to determine the extent of career motivation's mediating role in the influence of proactive personality and human capital on career success. Similar to the direct effect analysis, we assess the research hypothesis by considering a t-count value (T-statistic) ≥ 1.96 or a p-value smaller than the error rate (α) of 5% for acceptance.

In the analysis of indirect effects, our aim is to establish both the significance and the underlying mechanism of the mediating impact. The nature of this mediation process becomes apparent through careful observation of its effects. If the direct impact of initial factors on subsequent ones is substantial and the mediating variables also show a notable impact, this is termed as partial mediation or complementary mediation. On the other hand, if the direct impact of initial factors on subsequent ones is not substantial, but the mediating variable exhibits a significant impact, it is referred to as full mediation or perfect mediation. The outcomes of the analysis on indirect effects are displayed in the table below

Table 4 Indirect Effect Significance Test Results

Indirect Influence	Coeff	T-Stat	P-Value	Remark
Human Capital (X2) $\rightarrow$ Career Motivation (Z1) $\rightarrow$ Career Success (Y)	0.047	2.579	0.010	H5 accepted
Proactive Personality (X1) $\rightarrow$ Career Motivation (Z1) $\rightarrow$ Career Success (Y)	0.042	2.713	0.007	H6 accepted

Source: processed field data

The provided table presents clear evidence that proactive personality has a significant positive impact on career success, mediated through career motivation. This is evident in the coefficient value of 0.041 (indicating a positive relationship) and a p-value of 0.007, falling below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. The mediation is characterized as partial mediation, suggesting that proactive personality can influence career success both directly and indirectly through the pathway of career motivation. Essentially, this implies that fostering a proactive personality can be an effective approach to enhance the career success of lecturers. However, when career motivation is also high, lecturers' career success is likely to be even more pronounced.

Moreover, the impact of human capital on career success, mediated by career motivation, is noticeably positive and statistically significant. This is evident in the coefficient value of 0.047 (indicating a positive relationship) and a p-value of 0.010, which is below the 0.05 threshold. The mediation is characterized as partial mediation, implying that human capital can affect career success either directly or indirectly through the mediating role of career motivation, so the type of mediation is partial or complementary. The implication is that increasing lecturers' career success can only be done by building strong human capital, but if career motivation is also high, then lecturers' career success will be even higher.

3.6. Analysis of the Significance of Moderating Effect

The subsequent phase of analysis involves evaluating the impact of moderation. The outcomes of the moderation effect test are displayed in the table below.

Table 5 Results of the Moderation Effect Significance Test

Moderation relationship	Coeff	T-Stat	P-Value	Remark
Moderating Effect Z1*Z2 $\rightarrow$ Career Success (Y)	0.118	3.887	0.000	H8 accepted

Source: processed field data

The results from the moderation analysis, exploring how career management support affects the connection between career motivation and career success, reveal a substantial effect. This is apparent in the critical ratio (CR) value of 3.887, surpassing the threshold of 1.96, and a p-value of 0.000, which is below the 5% significance level. The coefficient of influence derived from this is 0.118 (indicating a positive impact), indicating that higher levels of career management support amplify the impact of lecturer career motivation on enhancing career success. Consequently, these findings support the acceptance of the eighth hypothesis, which posits that career management support moderates (strengthens) the influence of career motivation on career success among lecturers (H8 is accepted).

4. Discussion

In the realm of career success, numerous factors come into play, and understanding the intricate relationships between these factors is crucial, especially in the context of lecturers in Indonesia, where approximately 50% of lecturers have not attained functional positions despite their lengthy tenures. This discussion delves into the multifaceted dynamics of proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, and career management support, aiming to shed light on how these factors intersect and impact the career progression of lecturers.

Proactive personality, as elucidated by [42], encompasses behaviors and thought patterns that involve taking proactive steps in one's career and fostering innovation. This proactive disposition has been associated with higher levels of career success [55]. From an interactionist perspective, it is hypothesized that individuals with a proactive personality are better poised to achieve substantial levels of objective and subjective career success. This hypothesis is rooted in the idea that proactive individuals possess the capacity to actively shape their work environments [24].

In the context of lecturers in Indonesia, individuals with a proactive personality exhibit several advantageous traits. They tend to actively seek opportunities for self-development, engage in research activities, and contribute to curriculum development, potentially influencing the recognition of their achievements and, consequently, their progress toward functional positions. Proactive lecturers are also more likely to be engaged in research and publication activities, which can enhance their academic image and increase their chances of promotion to functional positions. Additionally, their proactive nature may lead them to take on leadership roles in academic activities, further bolstering their professional profiles.

However, it's important to acknowledge that while proactive personality is a valuable asset, other factors, such as university policies, fortuitous opportunities, and the quality of work produced, also influence career progression. Lecturers must navigate a complex landscape of variables to achieve functional positions, and proactive personality is just one piece of the puzzle.

Human capital, another pivotal aspect of career success, incorporates a mix of educational, personal, and professional backgrounds that elevate an individual's career accomplishments. Studies consistently demonstrate that dedicating resources to human capital profoundly influences one's career advancement [2], [3]. It empowers individuals with superior employability, knowledge, and transferable skills, facilitating their ability to seize promotional opportunities both within and across different organizations and industries.

In the case of lecturers in Indonesia, the level of education and academic qualifications significantly influences their ability to excel in academic duties. Those with higher educational backgrounds typically have greater access to resources and opportunities, which contributes to their career development. Additionally, research and publication quality play a critical role in career motivation. Lecturers with robust research skills and the ability to produce quality publications are more likely to be motivated to enhance their academic reputation and strive for functional positions. Furthermore, teaching skills are pivotal in an academic environment, as they contribute to lecturers' recognition and competitiveness for functional positions. Continuous development, especially in the face of evolving academic landscapes, is essential to overcome challenges and attain career success.

The dynamic relationship between proactive personality and human capital is apparent, given that individuals with a proactive nature are more likely to pursue self-enhancement and capitalize on opportunities for career development. This combination of proactive traits and robust human capital positions individuals to excel in their careers, negotiate compensation effectively, and seize promotional opportunities.

Career motivation, a driving force behind career success, acts as a potent link between individual traits and achievements. Studies suggest that individuals with high career motivation are better equipped to pursue their career goals and attain success [43]. This intrinsic motivation is particularly significant for lecturers in Indonesia, given the challenges they face in achieving functional positions.

Career motivation is influenced by various factors, including proactive personality. Lecturers with a proactive disposition tend to have higher career motivation, driven by their initiative in self-development, pursuit of opportunities, and determination to overcome obstacles. Career motivation serves as a mediating variable, bridging the gap between proactive personality and career success. It propels lecturers to continually develop their skills, engage in research and teaching, and achieve career milestones. This motivation, in turn, enhances their career success, contributing to their pursuit of functional positions.

However, the lecturer situation in Indonesia introduces additional complexities. Bureaucracy, the recognition system, job conditions, and personal satisfaction can either bolster or hinder career motivation and success. Lecturers may face obstacles in navigating these challenges, affecting their motivation levels.

Career management support emerges as a critical moderating variable in this context. Organizations play a pivotal role in providing career development programs and support to their members. Effective career planning, coupled with well-suited implementation strategies, is essential for achieving career goals. Career management support encompasses a range of organizational policies and practices aimed at enhancing individual career development. This support can significantly impact the relationship between career motivation and success among lecturers in Indonesia.

The presence of robust career management support can amplify the positive effects of career motivation, facilitating career goal attainment. Conversely, when career management support is lacking, even high career motivation may not lead to the expected career development. The bureaucratic challenges and limited opportunities faced by lecturers in Indonesia underscore the importance of career management support in bridging the gap between motivation and success.

In conclusion, achieving career success is a complex journey influenced by various interrelated factors. Proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, and career management support are all integral components of this intricate process, especially for lecturers in Indonesia striving for functional positions. Understanding how these factors intersect and impact each other can provide valuable insights for improving career development opportunities and enhancing the success of lecturers in the academic landscape of Indonesia.

4.1. Managerial Implication

Universities in Indonesia should prioritize investment in human resources and proactive personalities among lecturers, supported by effective career management programs. This holistic approach can enhance career success, benefiting both lecturers and the university. Moreover, recognizing the significance of career management support as a moderator variable can guide institutions in fostering a supportive environment that encourages career development and success among lecturers.

5. Conclusion

The quantitative study elucidates the intricate relationship between proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, career management support, and career success among lecturers in Indonesia. Drawing upon Career Construction Theory (CCT), the research establishes a robust framework for analysing these factors, utilizing Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to validate hypotheses.

Findings underscore the significant influence of human capital on career success, surpassing proactive personality and career motivation. Additionally, career management support emerges as a crucial moderator, amplifying the positive effects of career motivation on individual career success. These results suggest that universities in Indonesia must prioritize investment in human resources and proactive personalities, complemented by effective career management programs.

Moreover, the discussion highlights the multifaceted nature of career success, emphasizing the dynamic interplay between individual traits, organizational support, and external challenges. While proactive personality and career motivation play pivotal roles, they are mediated and moderated by career management support, university policies, and job conditions.

This research offers valuable insights into the complexities of career progression among lecturers in Indonesia. Understanding the nuanced relationships between proactive personality, human capital, career motivation, and career management support is essential for developing strategies to enhance career development opportunities and promote the success of lecturers within the academic landscape of Indonesia.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Author wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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